

Speculation on an Example of Maximization of Tsallis Entropy Subject to a Constraint Part 2 - Dual Probabilities and Frequency

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In Part I, we tried to provide an example of how Tsallis entropy would naturally arise from an example of a germinating seed. We focused mostly on the idea of creating a failure probability which could be maximized subject to an a priori constraint in order to find a distribution which represented a situation of maximum ignorance (which we considered equivalent to maximum entropy). This failure probability became the Tsallis entropy if one insisted that the $q=1$ case represent Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy.

Here, we wish to examine the notion of $f(ei)$ power q in more detail. In Part I, we noted that there seem to be two kinds of probabilities present, one represented by $f(ei)$ and the second by $f(ei)$ power q . In other words, there are two interrelated probabilities, with the second being an AND situation governed by q of the first. Here we argue that this suggests a frequency or cycling of one probability, namely $f(ei)$ with $f(ei)$ power q being linked with q cycles which reset themselves each time to allow for an AND expression $f(ei)$ power q .

In particular, we consider the case of a sunflower seed which readily germinates, but takes several (q) days to do so. We argue that this seed will germinate unless it is eaten by a bird or animal. Thus, the probability to germinate is tied to the probability for the seed not to be eaten. The issue is that the probability to be eaten, $f_1(ei)$, is tied to a cycle of a day because such a probability only holds for a day. If there are q successive days, then these are independent and the probability not to be eaten during the germination period is $(1-f_1(ei))^q$. Thus, we argue that the $f(ei)$ power q term which appears in Tsallis entropy appears physically in the natural world and is linked to processes (germination) which occur over several cycle periods (q days) with a cycle be linked with a probability $f_1(ei)$. In other words, $f(ei)$ only applies to the cycle period, hence the need for an AND product, $f(ei)$ power q for a process which takes longer than a cycle period.

Main Ideas of Part I

A main idea of Part I was that one wishes to find a distribution representing maximum ignorance. As a result, we argued that one could write a probability for failure and try to maximize it subject to an a priori constraint.

A second idea was that there could be two interdependent probabilities in a problem with the dependency taking the form:

$$f(ei) \rightarrow f(ei) \text{ power } q \quad ((1))$$

The third idea was that $\sum_i f(e_i) = 1$, but $E_{total} = \sum_i e_i f(e_i)^q$. ((2))

Here we wish to reexamine the notion of the two interdependent probabilities in more detail.

Interdependent Probabilities and Cycles or Frequencies

We suggest that ((1)) implies that there is a cycling or frequency linked with $f(e_i)^q$. In other words, $f(e_i)$ is a probability associated with a period of time (for example) and this period repeats itself in order to create a second probability which is linked with q cycles.

We try to give a possible physical example of such a situation. Consider the cycle of a day as a natural period/frequency which is linked to light/darkness as well as temperature considerations. For example it is generally warmer during the day than at night. Both the presence/absence of light and temperature can affect the germination of seed. Furthermore, the cycle of a day could have an effect on an animal which might wish to dig up and eat the seed. In particular, there might be a probability for the animal to find and eat the seed in a day, with this probability applying in an independent manner to successive days. In addition, this probability for an animal to find and dig up the seed may be linked with other physical factors which also affect the growth and production of a plant if a seed germinates. For example, a seed which is planted near a stream or in a sunny area may thrive and produce more, but such locations may also be appealing to an animal (which likes warmth or drinks from the stream) which may then seek the seed to eat it. Thus, $f_1(e_i)$, where e_i is the amount of fruit produced if a seed germinates, may actually be the probability $f_1(e_i)$ that an animal finds and eats the seed during a day. In this case, $f(e_i) = 1 - f_1(e_i)$, namely the probability that the seed is not eaten in a day.

Given a set of locations, denoted by i , one may associate each with an e_i , the amount of fruit produced if a seed germinates. It may also be possible to correlate e_i with the probability that an animal eats a seed in location i . For example, regions near a stream or sunny areas are not only good for plant growth, but may be preferred by an animal. Swampy areas or ones with very dense undergrowth of little trees etc, may be avoided by animals and would also represent bad growth and production areas. Thus, it may be possible to correlate the output e_i with a probability for an animal to find and eat a seed during a day. We suggest that in writing $f_1(e_i)$ we are first linking this probability to a period of time, namely a day, and at the second time correlating the probability for an animal to eat the seed during one day with long term conditions which are linked to the production of e_i fruit in that location.

Given this scenario, one may always measure relative $f(e_i)$ probabilities and normalize them to obtain:

$$\sum_i f_1(e_i) = 1 \quad ((3))$$

The Question of a Second Probability

In the above section, we considered the notion of a probability $f(e_i)$ for an animal to eat a seed during a time period of a day and linked it to the output of the seed if it germinates, e_i , in a particular location. One correlation is already introduced namely that of an animal eating the seed and the plant's output.

In order for a seed to produce e_i fruit, it must first germinate. There may be many factors associated with this germination process. If one assumes, however, that one has a seed which very readily germinates (a sunflower seed for example which is also one which animals like to eat), then one may argue that the seed essentially germinates as long as it is not eaten. One may further assume that once it has germinated, the animals (birds and small mammals) no longer wish to eat it. Finally, there is no reason why germination should occur in one day. It may take several (q) days on average with a very small standard deviation. In such a case, there is physical justification to write:

$$\text{Probability to germinate} = f(e_i)^q \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } f(e_i) = 1 - f_1(e_i)$$

The probability to germinate is based on the probability $f(e_i)$ for the seed to survive being eaten for q days. Thus, there is a physical frequency in the problem (the cycle of a day) which directly affects the probability $f(e_i)$, but a second interrelated probability (the probability to germinate) is based on the plant surviving being eaten for q days, hence leading to an AND probability.

As a result, we suggest that the probability:

$$1 - \sum_i f(e_i)^q \quad ((5))$$

is a measure of failure to germinate and is guaranteed to be < 1 as noted in Part 1. In the case of $q=1$, $f(e_i)$ there is essentially one probability and one should obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy and so ((5)) may be generalized to:

$$\text{Entropy}(q) \text{ (Tsallis entropy)} = \frac{1}{1-q} \{1 - \sum_i f(e_i)^q\} \quad ((6))$$

((6)) may then be extremized in terms of $f(e_i)$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)^q$, because a seed only produces fruit if it germinates.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I we tried to present a physical example of Tsallis entropy. In this note, Part 2, we try to strengthen the argument for the presence of $f(e_i)^q$, by arguing that there may be a physical cycle (frequency) in a problem such as the cycle of a day in the problem. This

cycle may govern the probability $f(e_i)$. For example, if one has a sunflower seed, then $f_1(e_i)$ may be the probability that it is eaten by an animal during a day. The next day the same probability applies again because different days are independent. The probability to survive q days is $(1-f_1(e_i))^q$. It is possible that a process, such as germination, requires q days. If the main impediment to germination is the seed being eaten, as in the case of a sunflower seed for example, then we argue that $f(e_i)^q$ is a physical probability for germination to occur. In other words, $f(e_i)$ is a probability restricted to a time period, namely a day, and so if it is linked to a process which takes several days (q days) and there is independence for each day, then $f(e_i)^q$ is the probability to use. Given $f(e_i)^q$, one may create a failure probability $1 - \sum_i f(e_i)^q$ which is guaranteed to be < 1 . If one divides by $1 - \sum_i f(e_i)^q$, then $q=1$ yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann (Shannon's) entropy. This may be maximized by an a priori constraint, e.g. $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)^q$ which yields $\exp(q e_i)$ which becomes the exponential function for $q=1$.